

Managing Sustainable Education for Social Studies and Economics Reactive Students in Post Covid 19 Era: A Case Study of Public Schools in Orlu Senatorial Zone, Imo State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

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The researchers investigated managing sustainable education for economics and social studies reactive students in post COVID 19 era: a case study of public schools in Orlu Senatorial Zone, Imo State, Nigeria. The study adopted a survey design carried out in public secondary schools in Orlu Senatorial Zone, Imo State. The population of the study consist of 201 (103 economics teachers and 98 school administrators) from the 98 public secondary schools in Orlu Senatorial Zone. The entire population was used for the study. The instrument for data collection in this study is a researcher made rating scale titled: Managing Sustainable Education for Reactive Students Teacher Scale of Secondary School Education for HIV Students Principal and Teacher Scale” (MSERSTS) with 20 items. Cronbach alpha statistic was used to determine the reliability of MSERSTS with index of 0.81. Mean score and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions. The findings of the study show that the result also showed that this both the Social Studies and Economics subject teachers do not have adequate knowledge of reactive students enrolled in school, and that there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of Economics and Social Studies teachers on the extent of their knowledge of reactive status of their students. It was recommended that principals, teachers and the Ministry of Education should provide a legislation that protects disclosure of HIV reactive students’ status to the school.

KEYWORDS:

Management, Sustainable Education, Reactive, HIV Students, COVID-19 PANDEMIC

INTRODUCTION

The novel Covid-19 pandemic inflicted mayhem on the global education system and their health especially the adverse effects on reactive children in school who found it difficult to get access to their drugs as a result of the global lockdown and heightened restrictions of movement. In line with goal number three and four of the sustainable development goals, to ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all ages and to ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all; COVID-19 has wreaked havoc worldwide on

children’s learning and well-being. Education is considered as one of the vital tools for national development. In 2013, the Federal Republic of Nigeria in her National Policy on Education stated categorically that Education is an instrument par excellence for affecting sustainable national development. One of the strategies in the process of economic development is human capacity building through education (Obasi, 2010). Education according to him, is one of the fundamental variables for human development through a well-planned education system, human capital is developed, and the development of the latent capacities of the human person for effective functioning almost sacrosanct. The truism that education is the surest way to sustainably develop any people or society needs no contention. Education, as I have already pointed out, is the process of imparting and acquiring knowledge, skills, attitudes, values and experiences in institutions of learning, while living, at work or play. The skills so acquired are subsequently applied to sustain present and future generation in their everyday life. It is the proper

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nurturing, transmission and application of such skills and knowledge that guarantees development and sustenance of the society (Abiodun, in Itari, & Ugbe, 2018).

Sustainable development in the work of Ilechukwu (2014) states that it is built on three “interdependent and mutually reinforcing pillars” of economic growth, social/human development and environmental protection and sustainability. Education for sustainable development is therefore an approach to teaching and learning based on the ideals and principles that underlie sustainability. The role of education for sustainable development is to help people develop the attitudes, values, skills and knowledge to make informed decisions for the benefits of themselves and others, now and for the future, and to act upon those decisions. Education for sustainable Development grows from a variety of sources and it is delivered through casual, informal, non-formal and formal strategies. Topics of sustainable development usually addressed here include but not limited to, conflict resolution, human rights, ethics, gender equity, poverty alleviation, peace, human security, citizenship, democracy and governance, energy, health, water, rural and urban development, corporate social responsibility, social and environmental effects of globalization, production and consumption patterns, cultural diversity, biological diversity, ecological principles and eco-systems, natural resources, management, climate change and disaster prevention (Bedawy, 2014). Education for sustainable development involves learning how to make decisions that considers the long term future of the economy, ecology and equity of all communities. UNESCO argues that education has a special responsibility to generate the knowledge needed as well as communicate this knowledge to decision makers and the public at large. (UNESCO, 2003). As a result, the body calls on all relevant stakeholders to review the programmes and curricula of schools and universities, in order to better address the challenges and opportunities of sustainable development. Therefore, contemporary sustainable development education is expected to orient on future development, ensuring proper quality of present and future life. Education empowers people for their roles in society. Therefore, reactive students who re thought economics and social studies in school are key actors in education for sustainable development. Economics and Social studies are both social science courses that deals with social behaviours, values, norms and managing the scares resources. It is important for reactive children to be educated for sustainable development because they are our future. Doing this will provide the reactive children with the opportunity to begin to value the world’s cultural diversity and appreciate the issues facing our world and of the impact they have on those issues (Itari, & Ugbe, 2018). Reactive students are children who are said to be infected with the Human immunodeficiency Virus (HIV) and Acquired Immunodeficiency Syndrome (AIDS). The effect of the virus requires monthly or quarterly visit to the hospital for

medication (Rosita Unique Care Foundation OVC report, 2021), within this to the hospital, they are expected to carry out viral load test to check the amount of the virus in the blood stream, undergo a counselling session with the doctor and attend their recreational activities like kids club; where the children are thought on how to stay healthy in schools and prevention knowledge on the virus spread. These reactive children also trained through their Operation Triple Zero (OTZ) on different educational handouts that helps prepare them to integrate properly into the school system without infecting other children, as well as their gender roles as teens.(Family Health International; 2015).

Reactive students has emerged as the single most formidable challenge to sustainable education, administrators, human rights, and development in the new millennium. Jaiswal, Magar, Thakali, Pradhan, and Gurubacharya (2015) suggest that School children of today are exposed to the risk of HIV/AIDS, which was quite unknown to their school administrators, teachers and their fellow students. The epidemic of HIV/AIDS is now progressing at a rapid pace among students in school. Studies have reported that young people form a significant segment of those attending sexually transmitted infection (STI) clinics and those infected by HIV, effective school-based education on HIV/AIDS ideally encompasses two elements: curriculum development and training of teachers. Examination of the school administrators and teachers’ knowledge of reactive students and how they interact with their peers is key. How they also participate effectively with the classroom teaching and learning is essential. Teachers play a major role in managing the increasing effect of HIV transmission and this can only be achieved if the principals or teachers have adequate knowledge of their student’s data. The factors that have contributed to the spread of HIV amongst students in Nigeria, include low level of awareness of young people, and inadequate knowledge of reactive students by school teachers, (Rosita Unique Care Foundation OVC report 2021). The post COVID 19 impact has not brought significant improvement in the reduction of the spread of the virus as these reactive students can now go to the hospital for their routine checkup. In line with Bankole, and Mabekoje (2008) the finding of her study shows another avenue of getting HIV/AIDS messages across to students and the community in general that has not been widely explored in Nigeria, there should be designed sustained educational programme for this reactive students in order to develop their interest in school.

In a report submitted by Management Sciences for Health (2012) it was observed that 92 reactive students who could not afford education or were dropped out from school due to non-payment of fees were block granted in some secondary schools in Isiala, and Ehime Mbano. A joint report by the United Nations Program on HIV and AIDS (UNAIDS), United Nations Children Fund (UNICEF) and United States Agency for International Development

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(USAID) in Mwoma, and Pillay, (2016) maintain that millions of children can be described as reactive due to the effects of illness, poverty, conflict, disease and accidents. The impact of the HIV/AIDS pandemic has been the significant cause of the increase in reactive students in school. USAID and CRS (2008) point out that basic education in primary and secondary levels contribute to the reduction of poverty. It increases labour productivity, improves health and enables people to participate fully in the economy and the development of their societies. They further argue that children and society who lack access to quality education are disadvantaged in terms of income, health and opportunity (USAID & CRS, 2008). Behavioural problems among reactive students coupled with lack of well-established counseling structures (Mwoma & Pillay, 2015) may negatively influence children's performance in education. Thus reactive children need educational interventions as they are at risk of dropping out of school due to economic hardships, reduced parental care and protection and increased susceptibility to abuse, and exploitation.

In Orlu Senatorial Zone, Imo State, Nigeria, most reactive students are out of school (Rosita Unique Care foundation 2021). Aside from the emotional and psychological effects of being reactive, CCFN (2020) reported that there is clear evidence that reactive children are dropping out of school at a higher rate. UNICEF (2009) maintains that addressing the educational rights and needs of reactive students in Sub-Saharan Africa presents new opportunities and challenges that need attention. Fleming (2015) pointed out that reactive students in countries with many cases of HIV/AIDS experience discrimination in accessing education and healthcare as stigmatization is associated with HIV/AIDS. Such reactive children experience financial constraints which further disadvantage them as they cannot afford the cost of education related materials; again, reactive children from child headed households are burdened with domestic and economic responsibilities, which in turn affect their participation in education in relation to attending and succeeding in school (Fleming, 2015). CCFN (2020) maintained that the school knowledge of reactive students helps in planning a sustained education system for reactive students; it plays a crucial role for transforming poverty in an environment where HIV/AIDS are predominant. A school manager according to Omenka, and Otor, (2015) is one who influences the behaviour of others (pupils/students) towards the achievement of a sustained educational goals at different levels. The management portion at the secondary school is occupied by the principals and teachers whose job is to ensure the responsibilities and specific task attached to his or her position are performed. Orji (2014) viewed education management to be directly related to classroom management and classroom discipline. A well-managed education classroom for reactive students has fewer problems with

students' behaviour and discipline. Therefore, the better you can manage the classroom, the better behaved your students will be. The best way to maintain students' behaviour is to have a well-managed sustained education classroom for reactive students, design engaging lessons; have clear expectations and consequences for the students' behavior.

The management of education for reactive students in secondary schools in the state has posed a big task on school management. The school manager is tasked with creating policies. Regulations, and designing patterns that upholds assimilation of all kind of children enrolled into the school system. Ujagbor (2019) stated that the principal is an active member of the inclusive school community with responsibilities such as the establishment, development, management, support and monitoring of the education for the sustained development of the student. Important in this respect is to set up an effective teacher support team (WCED Manual on Education Support Team, 2003). Managing sustainable education for national development involves the proper utilization of available human and material resources through co-operative efforts in accomplishing the functions of planning, organizing, staffing, directing and controlling Besong, (2015) also sees education management as a function of organization and structure, proprietorship and control, inspection and supervision. In line with the National policy on Education (2013), Effanga and Nwaoku (2010) captured the essence of education management to include ensuring adequate and effective planning of all educational services especially in the support service for orphans and vulnerable children, providing qualitative administrative and management control of this reactive children against discrimination and stigmatization through regular and continuous supervision of instruction. The educational implication of this, is that the actualization of these objectives is a function of proper management of human materials, resources available for a sustained development through education.

School administrators' lack of evidence about the HIV status of students enrolled in school pose as a threat for the school administrator to effectively provide a sustained education the school in the area of planning and organization for these reactive students as they mix with other non-reactive children in school. Principals' knowledge about these reactive students will enable them counsel and focus on measures to help these students fit in properly into the education system without transferring this virus to their association especially in these period when states are opening up their borders as a result of COVID-19 pandemic where most students have restricted to movement, social distancing and global lockdown. The school administrator can plan health education, growth monitoring, nutrition assessment, age-appropriate HIV treatment literacy, counseling, referral and support to these students and these services are essential services for reactive persons which can be rendered only with

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the adequate knowledge of those who are infected. According to Rosita Unique Care foundation (2021), school administrators assist students perform these specific role; Ensure 100% of infected children are on care and treatment portfolio in target LGAs , direct students towards overall technical quality - including adherence to technical standards, best practices in school. In collaboration with community based organization within the school environment, the school administrators can implement evidence-based health and nutrition interventions to this reactive students' household by responding to identified prioritized health, nutrition, and psychosocial needs. They can also provide regular supportive supervision to the students to ensure the achievement of expected results.

Theoretically, The Health Belief Model (HBM) is a health behavioural change model developed by Becker (1974) and Rosenstock (1974). It has been widely used to guide campaign design and implementation (Lapinski & Witte, 1998). According to the model, preventive health behaviour is influenced by five factors, namely; perceived susceptibility to a health threat; perceived severity of a health threat; perceived costs/barriers to performing the recommended response; perceived benefits of performing the recommended response; and cues to action. In the area of HIV/AIDS, there is little evidence showing the effectiveness of the model, but of the studies that do exist there is marginal support. Studies examining the modified version of the HBM have not always tested the comprehensive model with all variables such as security of infected children included, but have chosen to examine specific constructs of interest. Empirically, Nompapa, (2009) argues that to raise HIV/AIDS awareness, the school teachers, principals and school administrators should be seen as the obvious sight for educating adolescents on HIV/AIDS prevention

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

UNESCO, (2006) reported that Africa has one of the lowest education completion rates in the world, the low transition rate into secondary schools is partially a result of parents not being able to pay for a child's education especially for this reactive children who they believe do not have anything to offer to the society. Secondary schools are rarely free in South East Nigeria. Even in Orlu Local Government Area, Imo State, Nigeria where universal secondary education is guaranteed by the government, students must pay additional fees imposed by the schools. In Imo State, students must pay for Parents Teacher Association and other school related expenditure such as books, uniforms, and multiple fees for buildings, maintenance, desks, and so forth. Various mechanisms of funding have been applied by the United States Agency for International Development (USAID) and other development partners to support the education especially for these reactive children who are made vulnerable by the virus, including scholarships and block

grants. Scholarships are individual payments made to, or on behalf of, a child to pay for part or all of their education. Block grants are fixed-sum grants to local or regional educational systems or institutions that give the recipient organization broad flexibility to design and implement designated programs. As the number of reactive student grows, communities become less and less capable of addressing all their basic needs, including their ability to go to school (UNICEF, 2009). Lack of support in education by parents/guardians will have a direct influence on how reactive students perform in education (Mwoma & Pillay, 2015). Interventions to overcome educational challenges are therefore critical as a sustained education gives a child hope for life to work and is a strong protector against HIV to which these children may be susceptible. While different mechanisms have been used in various Nigeria (PEPFAR 2012), their relative impact on both the quantity and quality of education for reactive children has not been evaluated. International agencies have been vocal in demonstrating this risk; however, the question remains open on how to best to manage and meet a sustainable education for reactive students

Purpose of this study

The main purpose of this study is to examine managing sustainable education for economics and social studies reactive students in post COVID 19 era: a case study of selected schools in Orlu Senatorial Zone, Imo state, Nigeria. In order to achieve this main purpose, the following specific purposes were developed to.

1. Ascertain the Social Studies and Economics subject teacher knowledge on HIV and HIV status of their students
2. Examine the sustained education care and support service rendered by the school Social Studies and Economics subject teacher.

Research Questions

The following research questions were posed by the researchers in line with the purpose of the study

1. What is the extent of the Social Studies and Economics subject teacher knowledge of HIV status of their students?
2. What are the sustained education care and support services the Social Studies and Economics subject teacher are expected to perform?

Hypotheses

These hypotheses are formulated and tested at 5% error level.

1. **H₀₁**: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of Social Studies and Economics subjects teachers on the extent of knowledge of HIV status of their students

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2. **H₀₂:** There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of Social Studies and Economics teachers on the sustained education care and support service rendered to reactive students?

METHODOLOGY

This study is a survey design carried out in selected public secondary schools in Orlu Senatorial Zone, Imo State. The population of the study consist of 201 (103 economics teachers and 98 social studies teachers) from the 98 public secondary schools in Orlu LGA, Imo State (SEMB, 2021). The entire population was used for the study which makes it a census study. The instrument for data collection is a researcher made rating scale titled: Managing Sustainable Education for Economics and Social Studies Reactive Students Teacher Scale” (MSEESSRSTS) with 20 items. Draft copies of the scale were validated by three specialists from the field of Social Science Education and Educational Measurement and Evaluation, Imo State University, Owerri. Cronbach alpha statistic was used to determine the reliability

of MSEESSRSTS with index of 0.81, which was adjudged to be good enough for the research work. The researcher visited the schools involved to collect data for the study and also administered the instrument to the respondents and patiently waited for them to fill their responses. Mean score and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions. The basis for the decision for the research questions’ conclusion is that if the mean is from 2.50 and above, it is considered as agreed but if any mean is below 2.50, it is considered to be disagreed. The hypotheses were tested using one sample Z-test (also called Z-test of difference between sample and population means) at a $p < 0.05$ level of significance.

RESULTS

Research Question 1

What is the extent of the economics and social studies teachers’ knowledge of HIV status of their students?

Table 1: Mean scores of economics and social studies subjects teachers on the extent of their knowledge of HIV status of their students

S/N	Item Statement: the extent of the social studies and economics subject teacher knowledge on HIV status of their students;	Social Studies n=98			Economics n=103		
		\bar{X}	SD	Decision	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
1	We conduct health Education with our students	2.81	1.06	Agree	2.82	1.09	Agree
2	Can provide HIV counselling service for students	3.00	1.02	Agree	3.18	1.13	Agree
3	We teach students on water, sanitation and Hygiene (Wash) messaging	2.19	1.26	Disagree	2.16	1.19	Disagree
4	Have knowledge of community HIV services	1.61	.99	Disagree	1.70	1.09	Disagree
5	Adequate knowledge of ART adherence support, including transportation service	1.78	1.05	Disagree	2.16	1.11	Disagree
6	Age-appropriate counselling and HIV disclosure support	1.67	.99	Disagree	1.55	.91	Disagree
7	Structured PSS related to students conflict mitigation	2.20	1.26	Disagree	2.17	1.19	Disagree
Mean of Means		2.18			2.25		

The result in table 1 shows the mean scores of Social Studies and Economics subject teachers on the extent of their knowledge on HIV status of their students in Orlu Senatorial Zone, Imo State. The analysis shows that items 1, and 2 are agreed by the Social Studies and Economics subject teachers since the mean scores recorded by the items were above the criterion mean of 2.50. Items 3, 4, 5, 6 and 7 had mean scores below the criterion mean of 2.50, thus were disagreed by the

respondents. The mean of means are 2.27 and 2.35 for school administrators and Economics subject teachers respectively. This is an indication that the respondents conduct health education with our students, and can provide HIV counselling service for students but lacked in the following, teaching students on water, sanitation and hygiene (WASH) messaging, Have knowledge of community HIV services, adequate knowledge of ART adherence support, including

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transportation service, Age-appropriate counselling and HIV disclosure support and in conducting structured psycho social services (PSS) related to students conflict mitigation.

Hypothesis 1

Ho₁: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of Social Studies and Economics subjects teachers on the extent of knowledge of HIV status of their students

Table 2: Z-test analysis of difference between the mean ratings of Social Studies and Economics teachers’ knowledge on the extent HIV status of their students

	N	X	S.D	Df	Zcal	Ztab	Decision
Social Studies	98	15.26	7.66				Fail to
Economics	103	15.74	7.71	199	0.60	1.96	Reject Ho

Table 2 shows Z-test analysis of difference between the mean ratings of Social Studies and Economics subject teachers’ knowledge on the extent HIV status of their students. The mean score and standard deviation of the 98 Social Studies teachers are 15.26 and 2.18 respectively while the mean score and standard deviation of the 103 Economics subject teachers are 15.74 and 2.25 respectively. With a degree of freedom of 199 and the Z-test statistics application, it revealed that the Z-calculated is 0.78 while Z-tabulated is 1.96. Since the Z- calculated is less than the Z-tabulated, it

shows the null hypothesis is not rejected. The conclusion is that there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of Social Studies and Economics subject teachers on the extent of their knowledge of HIV status of their students.

Research Question 2

What are the sustained education care and support services the Social Studies and Economics subject teacher are expected to perform?

Table 3: Mean scores of Social Studies and Economics subject teacher on the extent of care and support services expected to perform of their reactive students

S/N	Item Statement: the sustained education care and support services Social Studies and Economics subject teachers is expected to perform;	Social Studies n=98			Economics n=103		
		\bar{X}	SD	Decision	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
8	Provide health, nutrition training and supervision of students	1.48	.76	Disagree	1.50	.76	Disagree
9	Ensure reactive students are enrolled on Anti-Retroviral Therapy	2.62	1.09	Agree	2.72	1.16	Agree
10	Teach gender base violence to the students	2.05	.72	Disagree	1.94	.74	Disagree
11	Provide post violence trauma counselling	1.76	.75	Disagree	1.99	.77	Disagree
12	Protect students from peer stigmatization	1.50	.71	Disagree	1.36	.73	Disagree
13	Provide structured safe place intervention for reactive students	1.40	.74	Disagree	1.60	.72	Disagree
14	Conduct PSS/life skill support activities for students	2.25	.75	Disagree	2.26	.79	Disagree
15	Adolescent HIV prevention services	2.59	1.11	Agree	2.65	1.18	Agree
16	Recreational activity(kids/youth clubs)	1.46	.70	Disagree	1.46	.77	Disagree
17	Child abuse case report to local authority	2.56	1.13	Agree	2.67	1.21	Agree
	Mean of Means	1.97			2.02		

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The table 3 shows the mean scores of Social Studies and Economics subject teacher on the sustained education care and support services that is expected to perform to HIV reactive students in Orlu Senatorial Zone, Imo State. The analysis reveals that items 9, 15 and 17 are agreed by the Social Studies and Economics subject teacher since the mean scores recorded by the items were above the criterion mean of 2.50. But items 8, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14 and 16 had mean scores below the criterion mean of 2.50, thus were disagreed by the respondents. The mean of means are 1.97 and 2.02 for Social Studies and Economics subject teacher respectively, an indication that the respondents ensure reactive students are enrolled on ART, Adolescent HIV prevention services , and child abuse case report to local authority for students but

failed to provide health, nutrition training and supervision of students, teach gender base violence to the students, provide post violence trauma counseling, protect students from peer stigmatization, provide structured safe place intervention for HIV reactive students, conduct PSS/life skill support activities for students and recreational activity(kids/youth clubs).

Hypothesis 2

Ho₂: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of Social Studies and Economics teachers on the sustained education care and support service rendered to reactive students.

Table 4: Z-test analysis of difference between the mean ratings of Social Studies and Economics subject teachers on the sustained education care and support service rendered to reactive students

	N	X	S.D	Df	Zcal	Ztab	Decision
Social Studies	98	19.70	8.46				Fail to
Economics	103	20.15	8.83	199	0.60	1.96	Reject Ho

Table 4 shows Z-test analysis of difference between the mean ratings of Social Studies and Economics subject teacher on the sustained education care and support service rendered to reactive students. The mean score and standard deviation of the 98 Social Studies are 19.70 and 1.97 respectively while the mean score and standard deviation of the 103 Economics subject teachers are 20.15 and 2.02 respectively. With a degree of freedom of 199 and the Z-test statistics application, it revealed that the Z-calculated is 0.78 while Z-tabulated is 1.96. Since the Z- calculated is less than the Z-tabulated, it shows the null hypothesis is not rejected. The conclusion is that there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of Social Studies and Economics subject teacher on the sustained education care and support service rendered to reactive students.

DISCUSSION

The study revealed that Social Studies and Economics subject teacher only conduct health education with the students, and can provide HIV counselling service for students, but failed to teach students on water, sanitation and hygiene (WASH) messaging, Have knowledge of community HIV services, Adequate knowledge of ART adherence support, including transportation service, Age-appropriate counselling and HIV disclosure support and conduct Structured PSS related to students conflict mitigation. The result also showed that both the Social Studies and Economics subject teacher do not have adequate knowledge of reactive students enrolled in school, and that there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of school administrators and economics teachers on the extent of their knowledge of HIV status of their students. Similar to this finding, Viswanath and Vandolph (2014), revealed that

mass media campaigns to promote healthy behaviors and discourage unhealthy behaviors have become a major tool of public health practitioners, school administrators, counsellors and the Government in their efforts to improve the health of the public campaigns focused on safer sexual behavior to date has tended to yield modest campaign effects. Further, Subhash in Ujagbor (2019) stated that HIV has no cure, but it could be prevented through awareness campaign in the school especially for the adolescent, protected sex and total abstinence from adolescence sex practice.

The research question two findings also revealed that Social Studies and Economics subject teacher agreed to ensure reactive students are enrolled on ART, adolescent HIV prevention services , and child abuse case report to local authority for students but failed to provide health, nutrition training and supervision of students, teach gender base violence to the students, provide post violence trauma counselling, protect students from peer stigmatization, provide structured safe place intervention for reactive students, conduct PSS/life skill support activities for students and recreational activity(kids/youth clubs). Also, there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of school administrators and teacher on the care and support service rendered to reactive students. This finding is in consonance with RUCF (2021) advocated that the school has a huge responsibility to care for reactive students and also protect them from peer stigmatization, as it can affect the cognition of a child in school. Therefore, it is the responsibility of the school administrators, principals and teachers to integrate these students properly with other children (CCFN 2020).

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CONCLUSION

Managing a sustained education for reactive students in the post Covid 19 era plays an effective role to curb the increasing spread of the HIV/AIDS and improving national development status. Principals and teachers can be said to be operative by the roles and services they concentrate to these reactive student and this can only be achieved when they have adequate knowledge of students who are HIV reactive, to enable them provide a sustained education services to ensure their proper integration in the school and the society.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations were made based on the findings

1. Principals, the subject teachers and the Ministry of Education should provide a legislation that protects disclosure of HIV reactive students' status to the school management.
2. Periodic trainings, workshops and seminar should be conducted for principals and the subject teachers on the different sustained education care and support services they can render to HIV reactive students without bridging the confidentiality status of the child status

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